

TDS Current Materials

Conventional glass fibre reinforcement, marine core and polyester resin technical data sheets

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1. Introduction

This document compiles the Technical Data Sheets (TDS) of the conventional material system currently used by AMURA in its standard composite manufacturing processes.

These materials represent the reference material system considered for comparison within the BioStruct project, where conventional glass fibre reinforcements and standard composite materials are intended to be replaced by flax-based reinforcements and more sustainable material solutions.

The compilation includes the conventional glass fibre reinforcements, the marine foam core material, and the polyester resin system used in AMURA's current hand lay-up manufacturing process.

The Technical Data Sheets included in this document are provided as received from the corresponding suppliers, manufacturers or document issuers. No additional testing results or material characterisation data generated within BioStruct are included in this document.

2. List of included Technical Data Sheets

No.	Material / commercial name	Supplier / manufacturer / document issuer	Type / description	Main information from TDS
1	Chopped Strand Mat emulsion EM 1002 / 300 g/m ²	Krosglass	E-glass chopped strand mat, emulsion binder	E-glass chopped strand mat made from 50 mm chopped strands with emulsion binder. The TDS includes 300 g/m ² as one of the standard surface weights, with ±10% tolerance, max. 0.25% moisture content and compatibility with UP resin.
2	Chopped Strand Mat emulsion EM 1002 / 600 g/m ²	Krosglass	E-glass chopped strand mat, emulsion binder	E-glass chopped strand mat made from 50 mm chopped strands with emulsion binder. The TDS includes 600 g/m ² as one of the standard surface weights, with ±10% tolerance, max. 0.25% moisture content and compatibility with UP resin.
3	WRS500M450 (3X1) Combi Reinforcements	Castro Composites / Resinas Castro S.L.	ECR-glass roving-mat combi reinforcement	Combi reinforcement with 1278 g/m ² total areal weight, consisting of 450 g/m ² chopped fibres and 516 g/m ² woven roving, stitched with PES thread. Suitable for UP and EP resins.
4	Gurit® Corecell™ M	Gurit	SAN marine foam core	SAN chemistry marine foam core. Suitable for polyester, vinylester and epoxy resins, and for marine applications including hulls, decks, superstructures and slamming areas.
5	Crystic® 489 / Crystic® 489PA	Scott Bader	Isophthalic polyester resin system	Thixotropic isophthalic polyester resin for marine laminates. Suitable for boat hull moulding, with rapid impregnation, good wetting characteristics and use with conventional reinforcements in hand lay-up processes.

Product information

Chopped Strand Mat

Chopped Strand Mat emulsion EM 1002

PRODUCT DESCRIPTION

Chopped strand mat is made from E-glass 50 mm choppeds. They are held together by an emulsion binder. The basic strands sizing contains a silane coupling system and excellent compatibility with UP resin. Products made of this mat are used in ship, boat building industry, transport and automotive, building and recreation. Emulsion mat EM 1002 is produced according to the requirements of Company Standard 04-WJ-00-004.

PRODUCT REFERENCE

	Example	EM 1002/450/125
EM 1002		KROSGLOSS S.A code for this emulsion chopped strand mat
450		Standard surface weight (density) [g/m ²]
125		Standard width [cm]

FEATURES OF THE GLASS MAT

- good tensile strength,
- easy handling,
- easy impregnation,
- low resin consumption,
- high mechanical properties of the laminate,
- Approved by:
 1. Lloyd's Register of Shipping
 2. Det Norske Veritas

KROSGLOSS SPÓŁKA AKCYJNA

ul. Tysiąclecia 17, 38-400 Krosno, Polska, tel.: +48 13 432 85 03, fax: +48 13 432 85 04
e-mail: kroglass@kroglass.com.pl; www.kroglass.com.pl
NIP 684-22-22-371 REGON 370497790 KRS: 0000237389
Sąd Rejonowy w Rzeszowie XII Wydział Gospodarczy Krajowego Rejestru Sądowego.
Kapitał zakładowy: 23.500.000,- zł - całkowicie wpłacony.

TECHNICAL CHARACTERISTICS (NOMINAL VALUES)

	Test method	300	375	450	600	700	900
Surface weight(density) [g/m ²]	ISO 3374:2000	± 10%	± 10%	± 10%	± 10%	± 10%	± 10%
Loss on ignition[%]	ISO 1887:1995	4,0÷5,5	4,0÷5,5	4,0÷5,5	4,0÷5,5	4,0÷5,5	4,0÷5,5
Moisture content [%]	ISO 3344:2000	max.0,25					
Wet-out time [min]	internal instruction ZKJ-IO-11-009	max.6	max.6	max.7	max.8	max.8	max.8
Breaking force [N]	ISO 3342:2000	min.50	min.50	min.80	min.100	min.100	min.100

POSSIBLE DEFECTS

- excessive concentration of chopped strands in the form of „nests” of max. diameter 100 mm,
- scarcity of chopped strands in the form of „holes” of max. diameter 100 mm,

The total number of defects defined above should not exceed 8 pcs per one roll;

- 5 segments in an emulsion-binder mat roll, each segment 4 m long, at least.

PACKAGING (STANDARD REFERENCE)

Packaging

Chopped Strand mat is wound on a cardboard tube (internal diameter 70mm).

Rolls of the chopped strand mat are packed into the polythene foil sleeve and then into the cardboard carton.

15 or 18 cartons with the chopped strand mat rolls are placed on a palette, 12 vertically and 3 or 6 horizontally.

The whole load is secured with the stretch foil against moving and damaging.

Labeling

Each roll chopped strand mat has label with information, as below:

- name and the address of the producer,
- type of the chopped strand mat,
- surface weight (density), width ,
- net and gross weight in kg,
- production date, production report number, identification number of the operator,

STORAGE

Chopped strand mat should be stored in a dry and cool place.

Best conditions are at temperature from 10 do 35°C and humidity between 35 do 85 %.

If you store the product at lower temperatures, please move it to the production area at least 24 hours before processing, avoiding moisture concentration.

KROSGLOSS SPÓŁKA AKCYJNA

ul. Tysiąclecia 17, 38-400 Krosno, Polska, tel.: +48 13 432 85 03, fax: +48 13 432 85 04

e-mail: kroglass@kroglass.com.pl; www.kroglass.com.pl

NIP 684-22-22-371 REGON 370497790 KRS: 0000237389

Sąd Rejonowy w Rzeszowie XII Wydział Gospodarczy Krajowego Rejestru Sądowego.

Kapitał zakładowy: 23.500.000,- zł - całkowicie wpłacony.

REQUIREMENTS, CUSTOMERS SPECIAL ORDERS

Upon customer request chopped strand mat can be supplied in other widths between 20 do 260 cm.

Chopped strand mats with other parameters needed (length, width, weight) can be produced after both sides, producer and customer, special agreement.

COMMERCIAL DATA						
Surface weight [g/m ²]	300	375	450	600	700	900
Net mass of the unit pack [kg]	45	45	50	50	45	45
Dimensions of cardboard cartons [mm]	1290 x 320 x 320					
Net mass of rolls on the palette [kg]	675	675	750	750	675	675
Gross mass of the load with palette [kg]	720	720	795	795	720	720
Standard width [cm]	125					

KROGLASS SPÓŁKA AKCYJNA

ul. Tysiąclecia 17, 38-400 Krosno, Polska, tel.: +48 13 432 85 03, fax: +48 13 432 85 04
e-mail: kroglass@kroglass.com.pl; www.kroglass.com.pl
NIP 684-22-22-371 REGON 370497790 KRS: 0000237389
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WRS500M450 (3X1) COMBI REINFORCEMENTS

TECHNICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Glass composition	ECR-Glass	
Weight per unit area	g/m ²	1278
Tolerance of the nominal value	%	7%
Dry thickness	mm	2,31
Composition		
Layer 1: chopped fibres	g/m ² length	450 50mm/38tex
Layer 2: woven roving	g/m ²	516
Warp:	roving	2400 tex
Weft:	roving	2400 tex
Sewing thread: PES 110 TEX	g/m ²	12
Sewing pattern	Trico, Gauge 3,5	
Cloth width (std) (1)	cm	125
Tolerance of the nominal value	%	±1,5
Type of size	Suitable for UP and EP resins	
Coupling agent	Silane	
Moisture content	%	<0,15
Roll length (1)	m	33
Roll weight	kg	55
Tube diameter	mm	76

(1) Other roll length and widths also available

SAFETY INSTRUCTION

Toxicological behaviour: Toxicologically harmless, non-respirable

PACKAGING

Pallet weight: 1100 Kg

Rolls per pallet: 20

STORAGE

In original packing: keep dry

Gurit[®] Corecell[™] M

THE MARINE FOAM

- ↪ Replacement for PVC cores
- ↪ High shear strength combined with low density
- ↪ High temperature processing (prepreg compatible)
- ↪ High elongation for toughness
- ↪ Suitable for all composite processes including prepreg
- ↪ Benefits from GL, DNV, RINA and ABS certification

INTRODUCTION

Gurit[®] Corecell[™] M is the newest addition to the Gurit[®] Corecell[™] range and shares the benefits of SAN chemistry common to all Gurit[®] Corecell[™] products.

- Environmental stability** - High tolerance for heat and chemical exposure
- Built in toughness** - High ductility and damage tolerance compared to cross-linked PVC and Balsa
- Fine cell size** - Resin absorption is very low, saving both weight and cost
- Superior uniformity** - Low density variation
- Eliminating outgassing** - Gurit[®] Corecell[™] eliminates the problems of foam outgassing
- Compatibility** - Suitable for use with all polyester, vinylester and epoxy resins
- No inhibition** - Gurit[®] Corecell[™] does not inhibit any epoxy resin curing mechanisms
- Handling** - Tough and easy to machine

Gurit[®] Corecell[™] M has been developed to deliver one product for all Marine applications. It provides a combination of high shear strength with low density, high elongation, high temperature resistance and low resin uptake. Gurit[®] Corecell[™] M is the perfect choice whether your application is slamming area or superstructure, hull or deck, using hand lamination, infusion or prepreg.

If looking for reliable processing, Gurit[®] Corecell[™] M delivers through the benefits recognised in all Gurit[®] Corecell[™] products of fine cell size and unique knife-cuts giving low resin uptake in infusion processes. For prepreg, Gurit[®] Corecell[™] M offers high temperature resistance to allow shorter cure cycles and the confidence to process without fear of inhibition of prepreg catalysis. Where static properties are important, Gurit[®] Corecell[™] M delivers high shear strength at a low density. Where dynamic performance is crucial, the high elongation delivers higher useful properties and the toughness to give impact resistance and superior fatigue performance.

Gurit[®] Corecell[™] M is available in resin infusion format and is compatible with polyester, vinylester and epoxy resin systems. The low resin absorption characteristics of Gurit[®] Corecell[™] and its unique knife cut formats deliver higher performing infusions, low resin cost and low weight. Gurit's global technical team have 10 years experience in resin infusion, hand lamination and prepreg processing and offer on-site support and structural engineering for Gurit[®] Corecell[™] customers. This combination makes Gurit[®] Corecell[™] a key part of a reliable package.

INSTRUCTIONS FOR USE

General working practices apply to these products, details of which can be obtained from the Gurit Guide to Composites or by contacting a Gurit representative (contact details provided at the end of this datasheet).

MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE

Type	Test Method	Units	M60		M80		M100		M130		M200	
Short Edge Marking	-	-	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Blue	Yellow	Black	Yellow	Pale Brown	Yellow	Brown
Nominal Sheet Size	-	mm	1285 x 2605		1220 x 2440		1130 x 2275		1015 x 2045		915 x 1830	
		inches	50.5 x 102.5		48 x 96		44.5 x 89.5		40 x 80.5		36 x 72	
Nominal Density		kg/m ³	65		85		107.5		140		200	
		lb/ft ³	4.1		5.3		6.7		8.7		12.5	
Density Range		kg/m ³	61-69		81-89		100-115		130-150		185-215	
		lb/ft ³	3.8-4.3		5.1-5.6		6.2-7.2		8.1-9.4		11.5-13.4	
Compressive Strength	ASTM D1621	MPa	0.55		1.02		1.55		2.31		4.40	
		psi	80		148		225		336		638	
Compressive Modulus	ASTM D1621 – 1973	MPa	45		71		107		170		317	
		psi	6480		10340		15570		24670		45977	
	ASTM D1621 - 2004	MPa	31		52		76		111		210	
		psi	4530		7610		11080		16100		30458	
Shear Strength	ASTM C273	MPa	0.68		1.09		1.45		1.98		2.95	
		psi	98		158		211		287		428	
Shear Modulus	ASTM C273	MPa	20		29		41		59		98	
		psi	2900		4240		5920		8600		14214	
Shear Elongation at break	ASTM C273	%	53%		58%		52%		43%		20%	
Tensile strength	ASTM D1623	MPa	0.81		1.62		2.11		2.85		4.29	
		psi	118		234		306		414		622	
Tensile modulus	ASTM D1623	MPa	44		72		109		176		334	
		psi	6440		10420		15880		25510		48443	
Thermal Conductivity	ASTM C518	W/mK	0.03		0.04		0.04		0.04		0.04	
HDT	DIN 53424	°C	110		110		110		110		110	
		°F	230		230		230		230		230	

Please Note:

Data quoted is average data at each product's nominal density, and is derived from our regular testing of production materials. Statistically derived minimum value data, satisfying the design requirements of various classification societies, is available on request.

NOTICE

All advice, instruction or recommendation is given in good faith but Gurit AG (the company) only warrants that advice in writing is given with reasonable skill and care. No further duty or responsibility is accepted by the Company. All advice is given subject to the terms and conditions of sale (the Conditions) which are available on request from the Company or may be viewed at the Company's Website: www.gurit.com/terms-and-conditions.aspx.

The Company strongly recommends that Customers make test panels and conduct appropriate testing of any goods or materials supplied by the Company to ensure that they are suitable for the Customer's planned application. Such testing should include testing under conditions as close as possible to those to which the final component may be subjected. The Company specifically excludes any warranty of fitness for purpose of the goods other than as set out in writing by the Company. The Company reserves the right to change specifications and prices without notice and Customers should satisfy themselves that information relied on by the Customer is that which is currently published by the Company on its website. Any queries may be addressed to the Technical Services Department.

Gurit are continuously reviewing and updating literature. Please ensure that you have the current version, by contacting Gurit Marketing Communications or your sales contact and quoting the revision number in the bottom right-hand corner of this page.

Corecell is a registered trademark in the EU and in other countries.

E gurit@gurit.com

W www.gurit.com

CRYSTIC[®] 489 and CRYSTIC[®] 489PA

Introduction

Crystics 489 and 489PA are thixotropic, isophthalic polyester resins. When used with Crystic Gelcoat 65PA, they produce a matched performance system for moulding boat hulls with outstanding durability and superior blister resistance.

The outstanding wetting characteristics of Crystics 489 and 489PA give rapid impregnation with freedom from drainage. They are suitable for use with continuous rovings, carbon fibres and aramid fibres. Fully cured laminates made with Crystics 489 and 489PA have high mechanical and impact properties and excellent strength retention in wet environments at temperatures up to 40°C. The interlaminar adhesion properties of the resins ensure that no loss in strength occurs at the interface between layers, following any delay in lay-up. Crystics 489 and 489PA are tinted blue, to facilitate easier identification and removal of any air trapped in laminates.

Approvals

Crystics 489 and 489PA are approved by Lloyd's Register of Shipping for use in the construction of craft under their survey, and by Det Norske Veritas. They also meet the requirements of B.S.3532:1990, Type B.

Formulation

Crystics 489 and 489PA should be allowed to attain workshop temperature (18°C-20°C) before use. Crystic 489PA needs only the addition of a catalyst to start the curing reaction. The recommended catalyst is Catalyst M (or Butanox M50). The catalyst should be added at 1% or 2% into the resin and thoroughly dispersed, shortly before use.

Crystic 489 requires the addition of a catalyst and an accelerator to start the curing reaction.

N.B. *Catalyst and accelerator must not be mixed directly together since they can react with explosive violence.*

The recommended catalyst is Catalyst M (or Butanox M50), which should be added at 2% into the resin, and thoroughly dispersed. Shortly before use, 4% of Accelerator E should be stirred into the catalysed resin.

The geltimes of Crystics 489 and 489PA can be approximately determined from Tables I and II:-

Pot Life

Table I - Crystic 489

Parts of Accelerator E to 100 Parts Catalysed Resin	4.0
Pot life in minutes at 15°C	21
Pot life in minutes at 20°C	14
Pot life in minutes at 25°C	8

Table II - Crystic 489PA

Parts of Catalyst M to 100 Parts Resin	1.0	2.0
Pot life in minutes at 15°C	60	24
Pot life in minutes at 20°C	40	18
Pot life in minutes at 25°C	23	12

The resins, mould and workshop should all be at, or above, 15°C before curing is carried out.

Additives

Since the addition of certain pigments, fillers or extra styrene may adversely affect the properties of Crystics 489 and 489PA, users are urged to seek the advice of our Technical Service Department before making any such additions.

Post Curing

Satisfactory laminates for many applications can be made from Crystics 489 and 489PA by curing at workshop temperature (20°C). For optimum properties and long term performance, however, laminates should be post cured before being put into service. The laminate should be allowed to cure for 24 hours at 20°C and then be oven cured for 3 hours at 80°C or 16 hours at 40°C.

Typical Properties

The following tables give typical properties of Crystics 489 and 489PA when tested in accordance with BS 2782.

Property		Liquid Resin	
		489	489PA
Appearance		Blue	Blue
Viscosity at 25°C 37.35 sec ⁻¹	poise	7.3	4.4
Viscosity at 25°C 4500 sec ⁻¹	poise	3.3	2.5
Specific Gravity at 25°C		1.10	1.11
Volatile Content	%	42	43
Acid Value	mg KOH/g	19	18
Stability in the dark at 20°C	months	6	3
Geltime at 25°C using 1% Catalyst M (or Butanox M50)	minutes	-	23
Geltime at 25°C using 2% Catalyst M and 4% Accelerator E	minutes	8	-
		Fully Cured* Resin (unfilled casting)	
Property		489	489PA
Barcol Hardness (Model GYZJ 934-1)		46	44
Deflection Temperature under load † (1.80 MPa)	°C	80	77
Water Absorption 24 hours at 23°C	mg	18	17
Tensile Strength	MPa	80	76
Tensile Modulus	MPa	3600	3500
Elongation at Break	%	4.3	4.0
Specific Gravity at 25°C		1.21	1.20
Volumetric Shrinkage	%	7.7	7.7

* Curing Schedule - 24 hrs at 20°C, 3 hrs at 80°C

† Curing Schedule - 24 hrs at 20°C, 5 hrs at 80°C, 3 hrs at 120°C

Property		C.S.M** Laminate	
		489	489PA
Glass Content	%	32.0	31.8
Tensile Strength	MPa	130	128
Tensile Modulus	MPa	7800	7700
Elongation at Break	%	2.0	2.1
Flexural Strength	MPa	214	212
Flexural Modulus	MPa	7500	7400

** Made with 4 layers 450g/m² PB CSM
Curing schedule - 24hrs at 20°C, 16hrs at 40°C

Storage

Crystics 489 and 489PA should be stored in the dark in suitable closed containers. It is recommended that the storage temperature should be less than 20°C where practical, but should not exceed 30°C. Ideally, containers should be opened only immediately prior to use.

Packaging

Crystics 489 and 489PA are supplied in 25kg and 200kg containers. Bulk supplies can be delivered by road tanker.

Health & Safety

Please see separate Material Safety Data Sheet.

Technical Leaflet No. 172.5

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SCOTT BADER COMPANY LIMITED

Wollaston, Wellingborough, Northamptonshire, NN29 7RL

Telephone: +44 (0) 1933 663100

Facsimile: +44 (0) 1933 666623

www.scottbader.com